

STUDIES ON THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT. PART IX

BY A. B. SEN AND S. S. PARMAR

The Fries rearrangement of five esters of carvacrol has been studied. The *o*-hydroxyketones obtained were further converted into alkylcarvacrols by the Clemmensen reduction.

The Fries rearrangement of carvacryl acetate has been studied (Eykmann, *Chem. Weekbl.*, 1901, 453). We have now extended it to five new esters of carvacrol, viz., propionate, butyrate, valerate, heptate and caprylate, which were prepared by the action of the appropriate acid chlorides on carvacrol. The rearrangement was carried out at 120° (without a solvent) using 1.3 to 1.5 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride. In all the cases studied, only *o*-hydroxyketones were obtained. The mother-liquor after the removal of the *o*-hydroxyketone was worked up for the *para* isomer, which was found absent. The hydroxyketones obtained conformed to Pyman's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) for *o*-hydroxyketones and were characterised through their 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. These ketones were converted into their corresponding alkylphenols by the Clemmensen reduction through the use of amalgamated zinc and hydrochloric acid.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Esters of Carvacrol.—The esters of carvacrol were prepared as described in the earlier parts of this series in yields ranging from 82.6 to 97.9%. They are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Carvacryl esters.	B P.	Ester	Yield.	Mol. formula.	%Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Propionate	121°/3 mm.		89.6%	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₂	75.31	75.71	8.26	8.74
2. Butyrate	133°/3		92.1	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂	75.94	76.37	8.91	9.09
3. Valerate	137°/3		88.1	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ O ₂	76.37	76.93	8.96	9.40
4. Heptate	158°/3		97.9	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂	77.61	77.85	9.46	9.92
5. Caprylate	178°/3		82.6	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	77.83	78.27	9.87	10.25

The Fries rearrangement of the Esters.—The Fries rearrangement of the esters was carried out at 120° (without solvent) as described in the earlier parts of this series. The *o*-hydroxyketones obtained are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Carvacryl esters.	Ketone formed.	B.P.	Yield.	Ketone.		M.p.	2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone Molecular formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found	Calc			Found.	Calc.
				% C.	% H.			% C.	% H.
1. Propionate	*R-ethyl-K**	164°/6 mm.	71.4%	75.26	8.29	75.71	8.74	14.08	14.51
2. Butyrate	R-n-propyl-K	142°/3	70.0	75.98	8.71	76.37	9.09	13.62	14.00
3. Valerate	R-n-butyryl-K	154°/3	65.8	76.56	9.01	76.93	9.40	13.07	13.53
4. Heptoste	R-n-hexyl-K	176°/3	73.3	77.43	9.56	77.85	9.92	12.28	12.67
5. Caprylate	R-n-heptyl-K	255°/10	60.0	78.0	9.83	78.27	10.15	11.92	12.28

* R=carvacryl.

** K=ketone.

Clemmensen Reduction of the o-Hydroxyketones.—A mixture of zinc (20 g.), mercuric chloride (2 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c. c.) and 10 c. c. of water was shaken for 10 minutes. The aqueous solution was decanted and the zinc washed with water. The amalgamated zinc was then covered with 30 c. c. of alcohol. Now to this 5 g. of *o*-hydroxyketone and 10 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath till a drop of the liquid gave no colour with aqueous ferric chloride solution. The completion of the reaction took nearly 8-10 hours. During this period 2 c. c. portion of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added after each hour of heating. Alcohol was then distilled off, and the mixture was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was successively washed with 2% sodium carbonate solution and water. The ethereal extract was then dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and the ether removed by distillation. The residual oil was then distilled under reduced pressure, yield 50 to 56%. The alkylcarvacrols, thus obtained, are summarised in Table III. (No crystalline derivative of these alkylcarvacrols could be prepared).

TABLE III

Ketone*	Alkyl carvacrol.	B.P.	Yield.	Molecular formula.	Found		Calc.	
					% C.	% H.	% C.	% H.
1. R-ethyl-K	<i>n</i> -Propyl	142°/6mm.	50%	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ O	79.78	10.06	81.24	10.42
2. R- <i>n</i> -propyl-K	<i>n</i> -Butyl	231°/9	50	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	81.09	10.21	81.55	10.68
3. R- <i>n</i> -butyl-K	<i>n</i> -Amyl	160°/4	52	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	81.36	10.48	81.82	10.91
4. R- <i>n</i> -hexyl-K	<i>n</i> -Heptyl	205°/10	56	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ O	81.87	10.98	82.26	11.29
5. R- <i>n</i> -heptyl-K	<i>n</i> -Octyl	168°/4	56	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O	82.01	11.12	82.44	11.45

R = Caryacryl.

K = Ketone.

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